

Making spatial pedagogy: using insights from spatial ability research to develop maker education pedagogy

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Conference Key Areas: 3. Student Engagement. Building Communities and Coordination & 15. Attractiveness of Engineering, Gender and Diversity.

Keywords: maker education, spatial ability, pedagogy, STEM, hands-on learning

ABSTRACT

Maker education has been shown to effectively raise children’s interest for STEM subjects. Creative maker activities, which mostly take place in informal learning environments such as museums and libraries, hold potential to teach children scientific concepts and train cognitive abilities that are critical to success in engineering in an engaging way. One of these often-overlooked skills fundamental to STEM is spatial ability, which is known to commonly function as a gateway skill to STEM disciplines. Spatial ability is malleable, and training can effect gains not only in psychometrically assessed spatial ability but also in mathematical skills, further demonstrating its importance to STEM learning. In practice maker education often lacks explicit pedagogical attention to the development of scientific skills and cognitive abilities such as spatial ability, instead overemphasising technological skills, and thus limiting its potential to increase learning related to science and engineering. Therefore, maker education practice would greatly benefit from a pedagogy that recognises spatial elements and scaffolds spatial ability development. In this paper the opposing pedagogies that lie at the roots of the maker education

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and spatial ability education are examined, as a prerequisite step to redesigning maker education practice. The final aim is to transform maker education practice into a STEM learning practice through which spatial ability development is scaffolded and can be assessed. This would help realise maker education's potential for scientific learning and may help a wider audience to meaningfully partake in STEM-related activities from a young age.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Maker education

'Making' is often described as using both high and low-tech prototyping tools to design and build physical and virtual objects [1]. Over the last decade, this type of activity has garnered significant interest from educational circles [2]. The type of activities that have come to be known as 'maker education' have their roots in the progressive and constructivist tradition of education and take place in both formal and informal education settings [2]. Maker education interventions in schools have been shown to successfully improved self-reported measures such as motivation for STEM [3]. Throughout Europe, South-East Asia and the United States, informal learning centres have also emerged in places such as museums and libraries [2]. Aimed mainly at children of primary-school age, and sometimes secondary-school age, activities in these makerspaces generally revolve around a playful process of iterative problem solving of an open-ended or challenge-based task with a strong emphasis on the children's creativity [4].

1.2 Potential for STEM and spatial ability learning

Educational maker activities have been ascribed significant potential to link science and technology learning in a creative way [2]. An important feature of these activities is the ability to break the commonly-held belief of a dichotomy between hands-on and intellectual work. Scientific concepts such as e.g., force, friction, momentum, motion, or electrical circuitry become tangible as they are explored as integral parts of the educational maker activities the children take part in [2]. Furthermore, children realise that they can engage with scientific matter, instilling a positive attitude toward science and engineering from an early age [4].

Fig. 1. Typical project integrating crafts and electrical circuitry from a library maker education workshop

Through the creative and constructional characteristics often found in maker education activities, there is significant potential for the development of spatial ability. Spatial ability is often overlooked in traditional education, but the critical role it plays to success in STEM disciplines, particularly engineering, has become increasingly clear [5]. For a variety of reasons, from lack of access to spatial toys to gender-related stereotypes, girls and children of low socioeconomic status tend to underperform on measures on spatial ability [6]. Through educational maker activities, children could be reached with activities that would help them develop this crucial cognitive ability.

2 DEVELOPING SPATIAL MAKER PEDAGOGY

2.1 Maker education practice – potential and limitations

The term 'making' originates from a movement of people gathering in shared spaces, referred to as makerspaces, where members of a community, club, or university can make use of shared traditional workshop tools as well as more technologically advanced prototyping tools such as 3D printers and laser cutters [7]. Maker education efforts taking place in out-of-school contexts such as museums and libraries form the bulk of implemented interventions and hold significant promise for reaching a wide variety of children [2]. Most maker education efforts are rooted in the belief that letting children explore the available prototyping tools will give children unique learning opportunities and allow them to express themselves creatively [8]. This mirrors the way in which professional designers use these tools to ideate and prototype to explore solutions, which is described by Kirschner as confounding epistemology for pedagogy [9]. Within this constructionist pedagogy, children are supposed to construct an understanding of e.g., scientific elements as a natural by-product of the self-defined projects in a makerspace [10]. In contrast to other forms of constructivist/constructionist forms of education such as project-based learning

and design-based learning, maker education activities often lack explicit attention to pedagogy [2]. However, contrary to this constructionist approach to learning, in practice maker education activities are often extensively planned and pre-structured by facilitators due to the technical skills required to make use of typical ‘maker tools’ found in makerspaces and the time constraints of (after-) school activities [4]. The current value of these activities to participants’ STEM learning is questioned by educators, as scientific learning is most often not explicit and not actively assessed, and if present, is subordinate to the successful use of the technological tools to create an attractive product during the activity or workshop [1][2]. Furthermore, studies on teacher preparation and effectiveness of maker education activities, both in formal and informal education settings, are not well-represented within the maker education literature [8]. Despite these current limitations, maker education holds significant potential, particularly as a valuable form of additional education in parallel to formal curricula, with room for multiple epistemologies; room for exploration and creative freedom, while also integrating explicit learning about scientific concepts in hands-on way, to bring engaging STEM-learning to a wider audience.

2.2 Approach to training spatial ability

Recent interventions aimed at developing spatial ability have generally centred around direct instruction aimed at improving the performance on tests measuring the psychometrically determined factors of spatial ability. One of the most illustrative examples of this is an extensive course that has proven to be effective at developing spatial ability among first-year university engineering students, showing that through well-structured direct instruction and scaffolding of activities spatial ability can be developed [5]. Similar examples of successful spatial training exist for younger age groups in primary school [11] as well as middle school [12]. The educational approach taken in these interventions is seemingly opposed to that in most maker education efforts. However, there is a good indication that construction activities with an emphasis on spatial elements within them will particularly help children to develop spatial ability [13]. The hands-on creative design activities often associated with maker education thus hold potential to not only teach scientific concepts, but also to significantly aid the development of spatial ability of participants. This could be realised by creating applied and hands-on instructional elements within maker education activities that specifically elicit the same mental transformations also elicited by paper-and-pencil tests that measure spatial ability. To effectively develop spatial ability through maker education activities it is crucial to develop an effective pedagogy for spatial maker education.

3 DEVELOPING AN EFFECTIVE SPATIAL MAKER PEDAGOGY

3.1 Scaffolding of spatial concepts and transformations

By emphasising and scaffolding specific spatial transformations described in the psychometric literature, similar to the direct training of spatial skills [5], maker activities can be developed to aid in the development of spatial ability. This could be done through making spatial transformations required steps of the activity and slowly

increasing the complexity of those steps as integral part of the challenges posed to the participants. Maker education can employ pedagogical approaches from crafts and design and technology education, utilising clear instructions and a strong emphasis on first sketching and copying, after which the reins are gradually loosened to allow for more creative freedom and increasing the cognitive load on factors of spatial ability. Therefore, activities need to be designed that take this type of spatial scaffolding as a core element of the activity. This will also allow facilitators to assess the spatial ability development of participants during the workshop.

3.2 Assessment of spatial ability

To develop spatial ability effectively through maker education activities, it would be beneficial to allow facilitators to assess the spatial ability of participating children during the activity. The assessment of spatial ability usually relies on the use of psychometric tests, as it relies on internal thought processes [14]. Especially within maker education, where constructionist pedagogy is leading and success is hinged on children's voluntary engagement with the activity, it is less suitable for facilitators to extensively test children with these paper-and-pencil based tests. First attempts have been made to develop assessment resources and strategies to identify children's use of spatial reasoning during play-based activities [14]. For example, through identifying the use of non-verbal cues such as gestures, movements, and creative output within the context of play-based spatial activities, educators' ability to assess spatial reasoning was improved, allowing for the children's learning to be supported [14]. Within a maker education activity this could for example be realised by assessing the performance on the scaffolded spatial transformations that are required throughout a pre-designed spatial maker education activity. For a facilitator to assess a participant's spatial performance on the targeted spatial transformations, a tool that allows a facilitator to assess the participants' spatial ability more informally during activities will be particularly effective. As this type of more informal assessment can happen during the activities, it will allow facilitators to intervene to scaffold the activity more actively with struggling participants with low spatial ability.

3.3 Professional development for spatial maker pedagogy

For this pedagogy to be implemented successfully, it is imperative to train facilitators to integrate these elements in their teaching practice. Therefore, future work will consist of an approach taken around professional development of educators, akin to training for spatial ability education [11][12], applied to a maker education context. Assessment of the effectiveness of the proposed pedagogy for maker education is centred developing a mixed-method design to qualitatively assess and co-design the pedagogy in practice, and quantitatively assess its effects on participants' performance on traditional psychometric measures of spatial ability.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The creative construction element of maker education holds significant potential for increasing spatial ability by exposing children to spatial elements in a crucial stage of

their development. This could be of particular benefit to those who are generally underexposed to activities and toys of a spatial nature in childhood, a group that is over-represented by girls and children of low socio-economic status. This short paper argues for the development of a spatial maker pedagogy that considers how to scaffold and assess the development of spatial ability. By adding a spatial pedagogy, maker education practice could be advanced from an engaging way to increase motivation and interest in STEM into a worthwhile STEM learning practice that fills a gap of creative craft-related teaching and spatial ability development.

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